

Contextual Spacetime and the Making of Classical Reality - Part 1: The Nature of Time

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What is Time?

Time is the medium in which “winds of change” propagate. It is what allows the contents of one moment to be different from the contents of another. For without time, there would be “no opportunity” for anything to change. Instead, everything would be “just as it is” in “one way” for all of eternity. For without time, the universe as a whole would not be a “changing” thing but a single “static” entity incapable of evolution.

The concept of “change” can therefore not exist without time as time is what provides the concept of change its axis. Much like how the concept of “length” only exists because there is a dimension of length that entities could exist within, so too the concept of “change” only exists because there is a dimension of “time” in which entities exist. For this reason, if the 3 dimensions of space were rolled up into just one dimension, then within that one dimension entities would never have a concept of “a change in position”. Instead entities would just be “on the coordinates that they are on” stagnant in their positions in that 1 dimension of space. Adding a 2nd dimension of time however would allow those 1d spatial coordinates to take on multiple instances of themselves on a different axis; an axis of change/time. In this way, they could then “change” by existing at different points in that dimension of time.

The Axis of Time

Take the example of a man named Bob who wants to walk a half a mile from his house to the market. In order for Bob’s position in 3d space to change from the location of his house to the location of the market there must be a non-spatial axis that allows such a change to take place in. For if there were only the three dimensions of space, Bob as a compilation of particles would not be able to ever “shift” his location from one point in 3d space to another. Instead Bob’s particles would simply remain on a single area in the 3d axis of space for all of eternity. The fact that Bob’s particles could ever “change” their positions in 3d space means that there must be a dimension of “change” that allows for Bob’s particles to be present in multiple positions of 3d space without contradictions being present. For if there were only the 3 dimensions of space and Bob was at his house and then the market at different times, then Bob’s position in space would need to somehow be situated at both (The L,W,H coordinates of his house) and also (The L,W,H coordinates of the market). Only if there is a 4th dimension of time can this “paradox” be resolved by Bob being situated at different coordinates in 3d space but each at differing coordinates in the time dimension.

To elaborate on this, when the axis of “time” is introduced, Bob can be both at his house and at the market with no contradictions being present. The reason for this is simply because Bob’s particles can be situated at his house at one point of time and then be situated at the market at a different point in time. For if Bob’s house is located at the L,W,H coordinates of (72,90,30) for example and the market is located at the L,W,H coordinates of (69,87,29) in space, then the reason Bob can be defined as being in both of those “positions” is because in the dimension of

time, he'd be at different points. Therefore if Bob is at his house at 12 PM but then the market at 4 PM, his position at his house can be provided by the coordinates (72,90,30,12 PM) while his position at the market could be described by the coordinates (69,87,29,4 PM). This is to say that Bob is no longer “defined” by his situated points in 3d space, but instead now able to “change” positions in 3d space within the dimension of time.

The above is illustrated in the schematics below:

3D Space Rolled Up into 1 Dimension (without time)

Bob - denoted by the rectangle (can only ever be at his house or at the market; he can never alter his position in 3d space)

3D Space (with time)

Bob can now be at both his house and the market just at different times. For each rectangle now represents Bob at a different coordinate in the dimension of time

The Block Universe Model and its Problems

This model has led to space and time being often conceived of together as one “4 dimensional lattice” of spacetime a la a “block universe” as shown below:

Such a block universe model of spacetime is helpful in terms of visualizing how entities could “move” through different positions in space. However, it does little in fully explaining the “phenomenon of time” (IE - why time only moves one way or why a single slice of it called the “present” seems to dictate all further slices of it called the “future” etc).

The Arrow of Time

While there is no consensus for what causes the “arrow of time”, it is thought to be at least somewhat related to entropy. Entropy or the measure of “uncertainty” in the universe is said to strictly move in only a single direction similar to time. For example, particles throughout the universe seem to always become more scattered and for this reason have the “configuration of their properties” become more and more difficult to figure out”. Even instances of particles becoming more orderly such when they are frozen seem to increase the universes overall entropy since the “freezer” assumedly releases heat into the environment. This constant increase of entropy is reflected in the “second law of thermodynamics” which states that entropy in the universe is always increasing.

Perhaps the reason that an increase of entropy aligns with the forward flow of time is simply because the 2 are a part of the same phenomenon - change. This is to say that entities change states in the first place not because they are “flowing through a dimension of time” but rather because they interact with other particles. When 2 particles interact they become “entangled” with one another and take on properties that become dependent on the others properties. An example of this entanglement is how a particles angular momentum can be dictated by its entangled pair. For if a larger particle with an angular momentum of 0 is split into two smaller particles and one particle is measured to have a spin of -1 then obviously the other particle has a spin of +1. This reliance of the second particles spin on the first is simply because since the source particle had a spin of 0, if it is broken up into 2 particles then their combination must have a spin to equal to 0.

Therefore as particles interact with more and more particles, they become entangled with more and more particles and therefore have their states become “dependent” on those particles. This creates an increase in complexity, where if one wanted to “find out” the state of a particle that state would be reliant on all of the states of the particles that it interacted with. For when a particle interacts with more and more particles it becomes reliant on their states and therefore has a state that has more and more degrees of freedom. Perhaps this is why time always flows forward, since time is a result of change and change is a result of particle interaction and entanglement. Therefore, when the entropy in the universes increases and there are more and more particles interacting with one another, the states of these particles become dependent on more entangled particles. Time therefore moves forward as entropy increases because time is a measure of change and when there are more particle interactions there is more change and time flows in the direction of more change or “forward”. This is to say that particles’ states become more and more difficult to figure out as time goes on because for every particle they interact with, their states “branch” depending on the states of the different particles. This “branching” of a particles state dependent on the states of other particles is conceived of as the forward flow of time in the context of that particle, since time’s flow is only experienced through changes in

particles states in the first place. Particle changes in states are therefore synonymous to the forward passage of time being realized and also entropy increasing due to the branching of its states.

Another Explanation for Time's Arrow

If considering a purely dimensional view of time, then another way to think of why time only “flows” one way is to imagine the entirety of every entity in 3d space “falling” through a dimension of time. Just as one who “falls” through the dimension of altitude would only move in one direction before hitting the ground, so too a universe that is “falling through” the dimension of time would also only move in one direction (forward). This would also theoretically explain why everything in the universe is traveling at the speed of light, since if the entire universe was “falling” through a dimension then it would presumably reach a “terminal velocity” and fall at a constant rate (which in this case would be the speed of light). While this is an interesting way to tie in the dimensionality of time, it fails to explain how things “change” and “fall” in the first place. For this reason, the arrow of time most likely has more to do with the “entropic branching” of information as discussed earlier as opposed to dimensionality.

Relativistic Properties of Time

One other known property of time is its' relativity. To elaborate, how fast time moves seems to vary for different observers depending on how “fast” the observer is traveling through space. For example, if an observer in space is traveling faster than an observer on earth, time moves slower for the observer in space. This “subjectivity” of time is what puts the “relativity” in the theory of special relativity.

This relativity of time can be visualized by “Minkowski’s light cone”. Minkowski’s light cone is a schematic that demonstrates the amount of space and time an observer could theoretically interact with at any given point in spacetime considering the universe’s fundamental speed limit of light. (Therefore if a particle is light speed away from another area in space it cant possibly access that space at the current moment). This can be seen by how if an observer is still then the observer moves in a straight line through the dimension of time. This essentially means that the observer is traveling as fast as possible in the dimension of time which translates to time moving faster for him. If however the observer is traveling through space then their “world line” will be at an angle which means that they will be moving through “less of the dimension of time” which means less time will pass for them. Similarly, if someone travels at the speed of light through space they then stay at the same point in time since the “angle” of their movement through space relative to time is flat. This essentially means that no time passes for them since they are moving only in space.

The most well known explanation for this kind of “time dilation” is attributed to Einstein’s theory general relativity which takes the concept of spacetime seriously as a curved fabric which objects exist within. Per the theory, objects with mass “bend” the fabric of spacetime which means that they then move “faster” in time as a result of the curvature formed by the indentation of their mass. As physicist John Wheeler put it “Space-time tells matter how to move; matter tells space-time how to curve”. This theory essentially explains gravity as the “impression” of spacetime that causes objects to “become attracted to” other objects with larger mass. The theory has also proved successful in the making of numerous predictions on how large celestial bodies rotate and also on the production of “gravitational waves”. The equations of general relativity in general seem to relate the pressure that mass exerts on space and the intrinsic pressure of space itself.

One alleged shortcoming of this theory is related to what happens at the singularities of black holes. Since the gravity of black holes would need to increase and increase towards its center, at the infinitesimal point of its center there would need to be an infinitely dense point of mass. This type of infinitely dense point of mass is not only inconsistent with how “location” and “energy” function in quantum mechanics, but also presents a “hole” in space time where curvature is infinite. Many physicists are therefore skeptical of the equations of relativity when it comes to this singularity.

Furthermore, since gravity is based on the “locations” and “velocities” of particles according to general relativity, then it fundamentally has a problem being integrated with the quantum mechanics idea of “the uncertainty principle” which eludes that particles definitive locations and momentums cant simultaneously be known. After all, if an entity can be in a superposition of states does that mean that the gravity would need to be at multiple points also?

Dimensional Contraction

In my opinion, there are also possibly other means of understanding of the phenomenon of “time dilation” and the differences in how observers experience time upon changes in velocity. Perhaps it could be that when an observer travers fast enough in a single dimension, their

movement in other dimensions simply slow down. For example, as a rocket in a nosedive gains more and more speed in the dimension of altitude it also travels less and less fast in the dimensions of length and width. Therefore, if time is considered a “4th dimension”, an object moving at faster speed through the dimension of space would also need to be moving slower in the dimension of time. This slowing in the dimension of time would make time move slower for the observer which amounts to time dilation on his behalf relative to the rest of the universe. Perhaps “ripples” that result in spacetime as a consequence of this dimensional movement could be related to gravity just as how in the model of general relativity, ripples formed by mass cause the gravitational pull between different objects. When objects travel faster in one dimension, that movement creates ripples in other dimensions that can be thought of as general relativity’s “bending of spacetime”.

The Past, Present and Future

While the above explanations of the phenomenon associated with time are undoubtedly helpful, perhaps the biggest mystery of time has to do with the subjective distinction between a past, present and future.

If time is in fact a 4th dimension of spacetime and an observer could exist on coordinates in that dimension, then the past would simply be slices prior to the point of the observer while the future would be slices post the point of the observer. The present in this sense would therefore be the “slice” of space inside the block of spacetime that is currently occurring.

The only issue with this is that it does not explain a mechanism for why the present is juxtaposed at the slice it is. For what is it that causes the present to be at that arbitrary moment that it is in spacetime? It is not enough to simply answer “because that is the point at which the universe is up to”. If the universe is simply an objective block of matter and processes, there must be something tangible to explain why the current “moment” is the only moment occurring apart from all other moments. It is not enough to say that “now is now because before was before and it has passed so we’re up to now.” There must actually be a reason why there could exist a subjective present moment in an objective block of spacetime. For there must be something that takes the 4 dimensional block universe and then turns it into “Minkowski’s light cone” (which explains the universe from the point of an observer). This essentially requires the existence of a mechanism that “separates” the objective block universe into subjective “Minkowski Light Cones” for observers. Therefore, the question is what causes this separation? What is the mechanism behind this contextualization of relative spacetime?

A New View of Time

The previously discussed models of time all undoubtedly help shed light on some of its most important features. However, there still remains a fundamental problem with trying to determine what causes time. In fact, even arguing that there could be a “cause of time” in the first place is nonsensical simply because the concept of causality is a result of time and therefore could not be the “cause” of itself. For example, the idea that particles interacting cause them to become entangled which is what causes a passage of time seemingly doesn’t actually explain how particles can ever interact in the first place. After all, wouldn’t time be needed for particles that are not interacting to interact?

Perhaps defining time as a marker of change may be the wrong approach altogether. After all, why is time even referred to as a marker of change in the first place? The reason is that it is assumed that without time, entities just stay in the same states of themselves with the same inherent properties and positions that could not change in any way. Time is therefore thought to be the phenomenon that allows such “changes” and is therefore analyzed as such. I would argue however that it is not “changeability” that defines time but rather “finiteness”.

This is because perhaps without “time” it is not that things “don’t change” but rather that things don’t “finitely change”. This is because anything that is changing states “finitely” has to involve time since time is essentially the “limiter” that limits the “states of things” such as position from infinitely changing.

This can be shown through the formula that calculates an objects velocity: $V = \text{change in distance} / \text{change in time}$. Note that as distance here is simply used to indicate the rate of change in an objects positional state, it’s definition can simply be extended to any other “changeable” property of particles. Therefore in order for a changing entity to have a finite velocity, time must be present to act as a limiting factor for that “change in distance” or state.

Now, perhaps the best way to understand what “time” actually is, is to analyze what would happen in its absence. Well if time doesn’t exist then there can be no change in time which would make the Δt in $V = \Delta d / \Delta t$ always equal to 0. This means that for any finite distance or change in an objects state there can be no time present to limit the change (since Δt is the limiting factor for a change in an objects state (Δd)). Therefore, without time to limit it, an objects velocity would simply always tend to be infinite since there is essentially nothing to “limit” the object from being in a “constant” state of objective infinite “change”.

This implies that in the total absence of a change in time (when time doesn’t exist and there are no separated moments), if entities do change states then they must do so infinitely fast and therefore have the “potential” to be “measured” as any state of themselves.

Time in this way would essentially act as limiting factor that limits objective infinitely changing entities in order to make the states of these entities conceivable and finite. This would suggest that the default state of entities is not “still” as it would seem to be intuitively but rather infinitely changing. Note that while it is generally assumed that in the absence of time, there can be no change in an entity’s eigenstates or distance, this assumes that the “objective state” of

entities is still while time is what allows them to change. However, assuming that entities are objectively still would imply that there is objectively one unchanging “universe” in which everything exists.

The Nature of an Objective Universe

For a moment assume that all entities are objectively still and only “seem” to be changing from the perspective of observers. After all, this viewpoint is thought to be the most intuitive based on how classical reality seems to function. However, as the universe by this definition would need to contain everything in existence, then what would happen at its borders? After all, if it is just “one” thing that is still, then it would need to have “borders” which define where it ends. That being said, any proposed “borders” of the universe could not really be borders since there must always be something that exists outside those borders. Even if one argues that there is “nothing” beyond the borders of the universe, even that nothing must be something and is nothing in name only. Therefore, it makes a lot more sense in my opinion to view the universe as something that is objectively infinitely expanding and “changing” rather than something that is objectively still.

Now the total universe as a whole itself must exist “outside” of time, since it can have no beginning or end. After all if it did have a beginning or end, then what came before the beginning or after the end? For this reason, if the universe itself exists objectively outside of time and time is something that is only emergent when viewing it subjectively, then it would make sense that in the absence of time the universe is not “one whole still thing” but rather a constantly expanding and changing thing. It is in this manner that time could be understood as “limiting” the constantly changing nature of the objective universe. In 0 time, any entity “inside” of this objective universe would need to be changing infinitely fast. It is therefore time itself that “tunes” this infinite change and seems to “slow it down” from the perspectives of observers who cant conceive of infinitely changing entities.

The Counterintuitive Aspects of Infinite Velocity in 0 Time

This notion of objective entities being “infinitely changing” seems counterintuitive as at least classically entities seem to “stay still” and unchanging in 0 time. However, because classically “time is always passing” there is no actual way to measure an entities change of state in 0 time. Sure, in 0 time the “distance” or amount of change in an entity’s state SEEMS to be 0 classically, however there is no actual way to know as 2 measurements cant be made in 0 time or in the same “moment”.

Now classically if particles are measured in “smaller intervals” their states seem to change less than when they are measured in larger intervals. However, when measuring subatomic particles their exact positions cannot be measured and only a probability of their eventually measured position can be calculated. Perhaps this can be explained by them continuously changing states in 0 time which results in their exact properties being unable to be “measured”. While this change in particles states may seem infinitesimal classically, that does not mean that the actual rate of change was continuously 0 or low for the individual subatomic particles but rather together they just continuously changed aligning with a “principle” of locality. This shows that

their actual “rate of change” could be infinitely fast in 0 time, but the actual change that they’re measured as aligns with a principle of locality that can be mathematically calculated.

Time as a Limiting Factor of Change

What this actually proposes is that time is not what makes things “change” but actually what stops things from infinitely changing. After all, if in the absence of time any change of an objects state happens infinitely fast, that would mean that time is actually not an initiator of change but a “stopper” of change. It is essentially what “tunes” infinitely changing entities to only change states finitely.

The opposite of this could also be analyzed. If there is an “infinite” amount of time that it takes for an object to change states that would simply mean the object is “still” or unchanging in terms of a defined state. This is because when its change in time is set to infinity, no matter the finite “amount” of change or Δd numerator, its velocity would always tend to 0 in $V = \Delta d / \Delta t$. What this shows is that it is not that in the absence of time things are “still” but rather that stillness is actually a feature of infinite time. This essentially flips the intuitive definition of change from a phenomenon that provides a dimensional axis for change into one that provides a dimensional axis for MEASUREMENT.

Time as a Consequence of Measurement

What this means is that when objects are infinitely changing states there is no way to ever measure them. After all, if an entity is changing states infinitely fast that would mean that it could essentially traverse any conceivable distance in 0 time. Moreover, it could also travel multiple distances in no time since if the Δt in $V = \Delta d / \Delta T$ was 0, that would mean that any addition of multiple distances in the numerator could be present in 0 time. For example, if a man traveled 30 miles east without any time passing, then theoretically the man could also travel 30 miles west without any time passing in the same moment. Therefore if another person measures the mans position perhaps it would appear to them that the man was still the entire time when in reality he moved - just infinitely fast. Moreover, in 0 time any finite distance D could simply be added to any other finite distance D in the formula $V = \Delta d / \Delta t$. This means that if there is no Δt in time, then not only can velocity be infinite for one Δd , but also for multiple Δds ($\Delta d + \Delta d2 / 0$ would still mean that the velocity of the object is infinite). Therefore, if an object could travel any amount of distances in 0 time, it could essentially be “everywhere at once” since there would be no way to limit where it isn’t at one time. This ultimately makes finitely measuring it impossible.

However, when time is added to the equation, now entities could be sufficiently “stopped” which confines their states. They can’t no longer travel anywhere and everywhere instantly but are now bound by the limitations of time. Because of these limitations of time, entities are forced to change states finitely instead of infinitely. Furthermore, if infinite time ensues, then entities can be “stopped” which is essentially what allows them to be “still” which is what allows them to be measured. In this way a measurement is an exertion of “infinite time” on an entity since it captures only “one” state of the entity. For example, if a car is measured at a certain point in space, that does not mean the car will be at that same point in space even a moment after it is

measured. However, in the context of the “measurement” that essentially took a snapshot of the car's position, the car is bound to “infinite time” since it can't ever change its position within the snapshot. For this reason a measurement can be conceived as the “infinite exertion of time” upon an entity. It essentially makes an entity's state infinitely still in the context of a snapshot in time.

Now perhaps, this is why time exists. Observers can't conceive of infinitely fast change since they are bound by their brains which are essentially “measurement devices”. These measurement devices therefore need to exert infinite time on objective information that is infinitely changing, just to produce “snapshots” with which they could “process” and translate into subjective information for the observer. Without an infinite exertion of time, such “snapshots” could never be taken by the brain which would mean that there would be no “moments” that can exist. Measurement is therefore the process of exerting time on objective information. Time is what stops objectively infinitely changing information in order to create a “stagnant” copy of it that can be utilized by the information processing system (or brain) of the observer and then be conceived.

An Example of Measurement and Infinite Time

Objectively everything that exists is just information. When information is conceived of subjectively, it is looked at a certain way and defined. For example, when one views information that their brain translates as “grass” they associate it with grass. However, the grass is objectively just information. It is only the human brain that defines and conceives information that it has translated as having properties it associates with “grass” to be “grass”. Therefore, prior to the “information” being observed and getting translated as grass, the information is not necessarily grass but can be theoretically constantly changing its potential states. However once it is observed and defined as “grass” by an observer, then to the observer that information will always be “grass”. In reality the information is still constantly changing its states, however when it is detected by an observer, a subjective version of it is stored as only having a single finite state. This is because “infinite time” (also called measurement) is exerted on the objective information which captures an informational copy of it as having the necessary states for “grass”. Objectively, the information associated with grass is still infinitely changing. However, subjectively, the observer has stored a copy of the information that has “stopped” changing since the observer measured it, casted infinite time upon it and then stored it as an “unchanging snapshot”. These unchanging snapshots are then utilized by the brain as the “informations” that make up experience.

Time is therefore not what allows the “grass” itself to change from green to brown or to be mowed or planted. It is rather what allows the information that the grass is to be actually “conceived of” as grass in finite time. Without time, this information would never become grass because it would stay objective, be constantly changing and therefore be indeterminate in terms of its states. Time is the phenomenon that occurs on the level of the observer that essentially allows what is always “objectively real time information” to become experienced sequentially by observers in a series of separate moments by creating “stagnant snapshot” copies of the objective information via the use of measurement.

The information however without time is therefore not “grass”. It is rather just information with no defined existence. In this way it is “constantly changing” and cannot be “defined” since what can be “anything” at once cant be defined. It can therefore infinitely change states from grass to trees to rivers to mountains in the same instance. Because there is no delta of time without time obviously, that would mean that all these potential changes would need to happen in the same moment which would mean that there is an “infinite rate of change”. Since observers can’t view this infinite ever-changing nature of the universe they are forced to view it through certain still snapshots called “moments” which is why time is necessary in “subjectifying” the objective information.

Why Is Information Infinitely Changing?

The reason objective information is infinitely changing is simply because there is no barrier or borders to slow it down. Since objectively there is only an infinitely expanding space for any conceivable information to exist in, any information within it could not have “borders” to slow it down in any way. The objective information therefore is essentially not limited in any way and simply changes states infinitely becoming “anywhere at once” in the absence of time. Time can therefore be understood as a “limiting factor” that takes objective information and creates “borders” around it which causes it to slow down in its objectively changing states.

An example of how this works could be demonstrated by how a super-ball is bouncing in a large space travels fast and continuously changes its “position” state. However, when a person comes and traps the super-ball in their hands, the ball stops changing position simply because it is now confined and limited by the border of the persons hands. In this way, time can be understood as a border that allows for the “capturing” of objectively information and limiting it into a confined “space”. This confined space is then what causes the information to stop changing.

No Borders;
 limitations, No Time;
 Entity Changes
 Infinitely Fast

Finite Borders; Finite
 limitations, Finite
 Time; Entity Changes
 at Finite Speeds

Infinite Borders; Infinite
 limitations, Infinite Time;
 Entity Changes at 0 Speed;
 Still

What is Space?

Space can similarly be conceived of in this regard as the “space” constructed by an observers subjective moments. The similarities across information in observers “measured moments” are translated as a “background” of space where that information continuously exists. However, in

reality such a “space” would be purely subjectively built “around” the subjective information that the observer experiences and not actually a separate “thing” in of itself. In this way, space can be defined as emergent just as time is emergent. It is simply a result of “objective information” needing a “background scaffolding” to be continuously conceived of by observers.

Defining space in this way establishes an intuitive relationship between space and time that can be used to explain their relation and the phenomenon of time dilation. Per this definition, when there are more measurements being made, more time is being exerted by the observer which essentially causes there to be “more moments observed” and more information for the observer to have to conceive of. This abundance of information requires the observer to build a larger background for the information or “space” in order to conceive of all of the information from these many moments. Now if the space that is constructed is subjectively larger and there are more moments being constructed, then from the perspective of the observer time will travel slower simply because there are “more moments” to be experienced. In this way, since there are moments being conceived of, there is more information to make sense of and therefore more space needed to act as a background of those moments. This results in increased space to traverse to, and an observer therefore seemingly travel “slower” through space when more time is present.

This is also why faster moving entities experience “less time” . For the very thing that causes them to observe of “less space” is the same thing that causes there to be less time. When there is less time being exerted, there are less measurements being made by the observer which thereby causes less “moments” to be experienced. If there are “less” moments being experienced there will be a “lesser” topological build up of space from the informations of these moments and therefore the distance the observer conceives of will be shorter. This ultimately means the observer will be traveling faster in “space” simply because space is a “topological map of information” and where there is less time there are less moments and therefore less information to conceive of.

The Quantum Zeno Effect

This model of time can actually be “empirically” demonstrated in what are known as “quantum Zeno experiments”. In quantum Zeno experiments, quantum systems are measured at lesser and lesser intervals (meaning that they are having their states measured more and more closely together in time). What was discovered was that the shorter the intervals in which these particles are measured, the less their states actually change and the slower their “unitary time evolution”. The reverse of this where less measurement cause the “unitary time evolution” to accelerate has also been demonstrated in certain “reverse Zeno experiments”. This phenomenon is essentially the quantum equivalent the old saying a “watched pot never boils”. Keep in mind, that as a pot is a classical system, watching it won’t make its minuscule quantum constituents actually change. However, the impact of “constantly measuring” a quantum system does seem to experimentally result in it changing less and less. Therefore it can be said that measuring a particle constantly, essentially causes it to stop changing.

In the context of the “new view of time” that I’ve presented throughout this paper, time is a phenomenon that stops change and emerges from the separation of “subjectively constant

information” from “objectively changing information” in order for observers to make sense of it. According to this, when not being observed, time itself doesn’t exist for the information since time is only a property of observer making sense of it. Therefore, any objective entities would seemingly be in “multiple states of themselves” prior to being measured (because they are undergoing infinite change) and condense into only “one state of themselves” in order to make sense to the observer upon measurement.

Perhaps in the quantum Zeno experiment, the reason that particles change “less” when being continuously measured is simply because measurement itself is the subjective exertion of time on an objectively changing entity. Therefore, while objectively the particle is always in a state of objective infinite change, subjectively the measurement device creates a “stillier” copy of the particle every time it measures it. If there are more measurements being made, then more “moments” would be present in the context of the particle, which would mean that from the context of the particle, it would change states slower. This changing of states slowing would occur simply because if there are more “measurements of it” than there are more “moments of it” and more time it takes to traverse the contents of these moments. Therefore, particles constantly being measured would appear as not evolving in time because their subjective states take “longer” to change since there are more moments being present since moments themselves are the results of measurement.

Another way of putting this is that if velocity in general is defined as the rate of change of an entity’s states then when the velocity is slowed it is because there is more time being exerted on a particle which causes its possible states to narrow. This narrowing of states causes the particle to then exist in less states of itself which translates to it “evolving less” within time. If the exertion of time is caused by measurement, then obviously “making more measurements” would cause more time to be exerted on the particle which would make the particles unitary time evolution “slow”.

Conclusion

While there are many theories as to what actually “causes” the phenomenon of time, understanding it as a “limiter” and “tuner” of objectively infinitely changing entities can be helpful in explaining how it appears to “flow” from the viewpoint of an observer. For if the objective nature of entities is one of constant continuous change, then obviously that would mean they are moving infinitely fast because they are “always in motion”. However, information processing systems cant conceive of objective infinitely changing information so they essentially exert “infinite time” on them in order to store “still snapshots” of the information that it can actually process and use to finitely conceive the world.

Time is therefore not what causes things to change but what stops copies of objectively infinitely changing information from changing. Assigning time to a dimension therefore just explains the phenomenon of how information seems to change within a finite space. It however neglects how such information would otherwise be objectively constantly changing states infinitely in the absence of any such temporal borders.

In the next paper in this series, I will illustrate how this process of “measurement” actually manipulates information and makes it finite *according* to certain principles which is what classically makes information appear as “continuously similar” and local.